

Chemical composition of late Eocene–early Oligocene corals in reef buildups from the Thrace basin, Bulgaria–Greece: Paleoenvironmental implications

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(Received: 20 February 2022; accepted in revised form: 31 March 2022)

Abstract. Coral whole-rock geochemistry and *in situ* LA-ICP-MS analyses of coral skeletons were performed on late Eocene–early Oligocene coral reef buildups from the Eastern Rhodope–Thrace region of Bulgaria and Greece. Coral reefs are locally associated with voluminous Oligocene volcanism in the region. The reefs are subdivided into (i) eruption-associated reefs (Krumovgrad); (ii) pre-eruption reefs (Ivaylovgrad); and (iii) Metaxades-Didymotycho reefs from field relations, trace element and rare-earth element (REE) abundances. Coral assemblages are dominated by *Cladocora* sp., which is accompanied by *Porites* sp., *Colpophyllia* sp., *Favites* sp. and *Leptoseris* sp. Eruption-associated reefs are characterized by their higher REE content than the lower in all REE contents of pre-eruption reefs showing negative Ce anomaly, and Metaxades-Didymotycho reefs that have lower middle-heavy REE contents compared to previous groups. Trace element and REE geochemistry of the coral skeletons indicates volcanic contribution to seawater, mostly evident in the eruption associated reefs, and contribution from terrestrial input in the site of coral buildup deposition. Contribution from a different source of prior diagenetic nature, along with subsequent diagenetic modification, is inferred. The increase in REE+Y (Σ REY) from pre-eruption to eruption-associated reefs is well correlated with elevated amounts of terrigenous elements like Al and Fe.

Bonev, N., Filipov, P., Stoylkova, T. 2022. Chemical composition of late Eocene–early Oligocene corals in reef buildups from the Thrace basin, Bulgaria–Greece: Paleoenvironmental implications. *Geologica Balcanica* 51 (1), 23–33.

Keywords: corals, geochemistry, Eocene–Oligocene, Rhodope–Thrace region, Bulgaria, Greece.

INTRODUCTION

The Thrace basin represents a wide syn- and post-tectonic depression exposed on the territories of Bulgaria, Greece and Turkey, which is filled by different facies and composition Eocene to Quaternary sedimentary successions reaching a thickness of up to 9 km (Kopp, 1961; Siyako *et al.*, 1989; Okay

et al., 1991; Boyanov and Goranov, 2001). Upper Eocene (Priabonian) and Oligocene carbonate sedimentary sections in this basin contain reef buildups, whose construction predates or is coeval with the voluminous post-collisional Oligocene volcanism (Harkovska *et al.*, 1989; Christofides *et al.*, 2004; Marchev *et al.*, 2010) in the Eastern Rhodope–Thrace region (Fig. 1). Reef buildups have been reported

Fig. 1. Synthetic geological map of the Eastern Rhodope–Thrace region in Bulgaria and Greece (modified after Bonev and Becalotto, 2007). Inset: tectonic framework of the Alpine orogen in the northern Aegean region of the Eastern Mediterranean region.

in distinct locations of the Eastern Rhodope area of Bulgaria close to the towns of Krumovgrad and Ivaylovgrad (Boyanov and Goranov, 2001; Sarov *et al.*, 2007, 2008), and in the Thrace area of Northern Greece, where they were reported near the towns of Didymotycho and Soufli (Papadopoulos, 1982; Papadopoulos and Anastasiadis, 2002; Kołodziej and Marcopoulou-Diacantoni, 2003). In the Eastern Rhodope area, the corals have not been taxonomically determined in the reef buildups, and they were only described in the explanatory notes associated with molluscs, bivalves, echinoids, algae and foraminifers. A single taxonomic study of coral-bearing reef buildups in Northern Greece (Kołodziej and Marcopoulou-Diacantoni, 2003) has identified upper Eocene (Priabonian) massive corals of the genera *Favites* and *Porites*, branched corals of the genus *Acropora*, Oligocene colonial corals of the genus *Caulastraea* and massive corals of the genera *Astreopora*, *Alveopora* and *Goniopora*.

Corals are sensitive organisms, which play a key role in the record of environmental changes in ancient and modern seas and oceanic basins (Roberts *et al.*, 2009), but studying ancient environments and making reconstructions on fossil reefs is always challenging. Decoding the geochemical signature of fossil coral skeletons can provide useful information about diagenetic history or even original chemical composition of the skeletons reflecting (1) the initial element concentrations inherited from the seawater source (Li and Jones, 2014; Luo *et al.*, 2021), (2) possible detrital input (Barnard *et al.*, 1974), and/or (3) clues to drastic changes in the environment conditions caused by the coeval Oligocene eruptions that could have impacted significantly the development of the reef edifices (Wu *et al.*, 2018). In this regard, trace element and rare earth composition of fossil skeletons and further comparison with different sources could provide important insights when it comes to studying depositional paleoenvironmental conditions.

ronmental contamination masked behind diagenetic changes.

In this paper, we combine field data, whole-rock major element geochemistry of corals and coral skeleton, *in-situ* laser ablation inductively coupled mass-spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS), and trace and rare earth element (REE) geochemistry of late Eocene–early Oligocene reefal buildups in the Thrace basin of Bulgaria and Greece. Our goal is to possibly identify the geochemical fingerprint of the original sedimentary environment on the chemical composition of the corals and the way their skeletons have been geochemically modified through diagenetic alteration, which would allow us to establish the conditions of taphonomy and pollution of the seawater resulting from the Oligocene volcanism.

GEOLOGICAL SETTING

The pre-Paleogene metamorphic basement of the Eastern Rhodope–Thrace region experienced syn- to post-orogenic crustal extension during the Eocene (*e.g.*, Bonev and Beccalotto, 2007; Fig. 1). Maastrichtian–Paleocene clastic sedimentary rocks (*e.g.*, Boyanov and Goranov, 2001) with syn-tectonic hanging wall nature provide the onset of crustal extension, with a minimum age indicated by biostratigraphically youngest early Eocene (Ypresian) unconformable strata as discussed by Bonev *et al.* (2006). Extensional exhumation from the metamorphic hanging wall to the footwall of the extensional fault system followed progressive Paleocene to late Eocene cooling history as derived from $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ ages in the range of 64.7 Ma to 34.1 Ma (Bonev and Stampfli, 2011; Bonev *et al.*, 2013).

In the Eastern Rhodope–Thrace region, the early–middle to late Eocene sedimentary successions consist of clastic, clayey and carbonate sedimentary rocks (Papadopoulos, 1980, 1982; Boyanov and Goranov, 2001; Chatalov *et al.*, 2015), which represent renewed cycles of deposition lying unconformably upon the hanging wall and accumulated in fault-bounded half-grabens that have also propagated into the footwall. In the Eastern Rhodope area, Boyanov and Goranov (2001) unified the early–middle(?) Eocene clastic deposits into an informal breccia-conglomerate unit, unconformably overlying the metamorphic basement and the Maastrichtian–Paleocene sedimentary rocks. The breccia-conglomerate unit in turn is conformably unconformably overlain by a coal-bearing sandy unit and unconformably overlain by a marl-limestone unit, with both units of proven late Eocene age by means

of mollusks and foraminifers. According to Boyanov and Goranov (2001), the small reefs started to accumulate within the coal-bearing sandy unit, but mainly occur within the marl-limestone unit.

The voluminous late Eocene–Oligocene post-collisional volcanism in the Eastern Rhodope area of South Bulgaria was initially identified to span 37–25.5 Ma by K-Ar ages of numerous paleovolcanoes (Lilov *et al.*, 1987). Subsequently, the timing of volcanism was refined by $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ ages to spread essentially in the early Oligocene between 34.62 ± 0.46 Ma and 31.13 ± 0.12 Ma (*e.g.*, Marchev *et al.*, 2010). In the Thrace area of Northern Greece, the temporal spread of the Oligocene volcanism is bracketed between 33.5 Ma and 25.4 Ma as derived from K-Ar ages (Christofides *et al.*, 2004). In both areas, the Oligocene volcanic products are associated with a similar in age shallow-marine sedimentary and volcano-sedimentary rocks.

The Neogene (Miocene–Pliocene) terrestrial deposits represent the latest sedimentary cover consisting of alluvial and fluvial-lacustrine clastic and clayey sedimentary rocks (Boyanov and Goranov, 2001).

FIELD DATA, SAMPLES AND CORAL ASSEMBLAGE

Our study focused on coral-bearing reef buildups exposed close to the town of Ivaylovgrad and the town of Krumovgrad in the Eastern Rhodope area of Southern Bulgaria, and others located at the town of Didymotycho and near the village of Metaxades in the Thrace area of Northern Greece (Fig. 1). The ten samples from six locations mentioned below refer to the ones shown in Fig. 1, and they were used for geochemistry. Part of the samples and their coral assemblages are depicted in Fig. 2.

At Ivaylovgrad, the marl-limestone unit exposes a large fragment of a reef buildup and, to the south, other smaller reef fragments are also preserved. The reef at Ivaylovgrad (location K4) consists of a massive limestone containing corals, bivalves, gastropods and echinoids, from which sample K4 represents a single skeleton of *Cladocora* sp. Further south at location K2, the unconformable position of the marl-limestone unit over the coal-bearing sandy unit is well exposed, and at this location the marl-limestone unit shows richer coral assemblage. There, the massive limestone contains corals, gastropods, echinids and algae. Among the coral assemblage were identified *Colpophyllia* sp., *Porites* sp. and *Cladocora* sp. The *Colpophyllia* sp. forms

Fig. 2. Photographs of the corals in some of the studied samples.

colonies (sample K2a; Fig. 2b), *Porites* sp. occurs as single coral skeletons (sample K2b), and *Cladocora* sp. forms single coral branches and colonies (sample K2; Fig. 2a). At location K3 further south, the same unit and rocks contain single skeletons of *Cladocora* sp. (sample K3). Cold-cathodoluminescence (cold-CL) imaging was performed on cross-

sections of coral branches sampled in the above mentioned locations (Fig. 3a–c).

West of the town of Krumovgrad, the Eocene sedimentary rock formations are also present and well exposed, with similar unconformable to each other relationships. However, the coal-bearing sandy unit and marl-limestone unit are covered

Fig. 3. a) Recrystallized coral colony, where the skeleton and original porosity have been replaced and filled by calcite; b) Pores filled by oscillatory calcite within the recrystallized coral skeleton; c) Thermal diagenetic recrystallization of a coral with coarse-grained oscillatory calcite; d) Finely recrystallized calcite cement embracing foraminifera within the coral pores.

by tuffs and lavas of the Irantepe paleovolcano ($^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ ages from 34.62 ± 0.46 Ma to 32.80 ± 0.28 Ma) and the Zvezdel paleovolcano ($^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ ages 33.18 ± 0.46 Ma and 33.03 ± 0.87 Ma; see Bonev *et al.*, 2013). In the field, the volcanic products of the Zvezdel paleovolcano directly overlie the marl-limestone unit. In this unit, the limestone contains mostly *Cladocora* sp. colonies and rare single *Cladocora* sp. skeletons (sample K6a; Fig. 2c) and single skeletons of *Porites* sp. (sample K6; Fig. 2d). Cold-CL images of *Porites* sp. (sample K6) are shown in Fig. 3d to embrace foraminifera findings.

At Didymotycho (locality D), in the Thrace area of Northern Greece, the large reef buildup lies on conglomerate and sandstone consisting mostly of clasts derived from the underlying Middle Jurassic Evros ophiolite (*e.g.*, Bonev and Stampfli, 2011). Other small outcrops of reef buildups are also exposed in proximity. The late Eocene sedimentary units exposed at Didymotycho are considered as

equivalents to the coal-bearing sandy unit and marl-limestone unit from the Eastern Rhodope area. There, the reef-building massive limestone contains corals, algae, bivalves and mollusks. Abundant single skeletons and colonial *Cladocora* sp. were identified (sample D; Fig. 2e).

In the same area, south of the village of Metaxades, the late Eocene sedimentary successions are analogous to the coal-bearing sandy unit and marl-limestone unit, which are exposed immediately to the west in the Eastern Rhodope area in Bulgaria. The reefal massive limestone occurs as a thin lenticular body overlying the conglomerate and sandstone consisting of metamorphic basement clasts. In locality M, the limestone contains colonies of *Favites* sp. (sample M1) and *Leptoseris* sp. (sample M; Fig. 2f).

Based on field relations, the reefs can be subdivided into eruption-associated reefs (Krumovgrad) and pre-eruption reefs (Ivaylovgrad, Metaxades).

GEOCHEMISTRY

Whole-rock major element analyses by X-ray fluorescence were performed on a PANalytical (EDXRF, Epsilon 3XLE, Omnia 3SW) instrument at the University of Sofia “St Kliment Ohridski”, Bulgaria, and the analytical results are listed in Table 1, together with the sample locations. XRF analyses were conducted on fused disks of powdered material from the samples of coral skeletons. The fused beads were prepared by mixing approximately 1 g of sample with 3 g of lithium metaborate (LiBO_2) and 6 g of lithium tetraborate ($\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$) flux. The melting process was realized using a Claisse LeNeo Fused Bead maker, in 5% Au–95% Pt casting bowls at 1065 °C. The loss of ignition (LOI) at 1000 °C was expressed as a percentage of sample weight dried in an oven at 110 °C overnight. Analytical errors for major oxides are within the range of 1%. LA-ICP-MS analyses of trace elements and REE were performed *in-situ* on individual coral skeletons of each sample. Analytical procedures and the facility for LA-ICP-MS analyses are the same as described in Bonev *et al.* (2019).

The major element contents define carbonaceous, limy composition of the studied corals, and consecutively for their host rocks. SiO_2 contents in the samples vary from 0.49 to 2.70 wt.%, implying that some samples (*e.g.*, M, K4, K6a) have probably suffered a slight silicification. Other major oxides of relatively high abundances in the coral skeletons are MgO , Al_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 (Table 1).

The most distinctive characteristics of the coral skeleton chemistry are found in the REE content. In general, the studied samples show particularly elevated REE concentrations for the eruption-associated reefs (sample K6, Table 1). Normalized to post-Archean Australian shale (PAAS) (Taylor and McLennan, 1985) the patterns of the samples demonstrate higher REE in eruption-associated reefs compared to the pre-eruption reefs of distinctly lower light REE (Fig. 4). In addition, the pre-eruption reefs demonstrate a well-pronounced negative Ce anomaly. Metaxades and Didymotycho samples have lower middle and heavy REE concentrations relative to 1) partially the pre-eruption (Ivaylovgrad) and 2) all the eruption-associated reefs (Krumovgrad). Furthermore, the samples can be divided in three groups according to their normalized REE patterns in particular. The first group includes part of the samples of the pre-eruption reefs that are characterized by positive La and negative Ce anomalies and depleted in light REE (La to Nd) relative to the middle REE (Sm to Ho). The

second group comprises the rest of the pre-eruption reefs, the Metaxades and Didymotycho samples, as well as partially the eruption-associated corals that exhibit substantially higher REE concentration, less pronounced Ce anomaly and enrichment in heavy REE (Er to Lu) in respect to the light REE. The third group is restricted to only one sample of eruption-associated reefs, which is characterized by enrichment in light REE relative to the heavy REE.

Those three groups are also recognizable by the trace element variations in the diagrams in Fig. 5. Samples from the eruption-associated reefs are richer in Al, Fe, Mg and REE+Y (ΣREEY), while the samples of pre-eruption corals are richer in Ba. The abundances of Mn and Sr are not linked to any trends between different groups.

DISCUSSION

Lower silica contents (<1 wt.%) in the coral interseptal space can be the result of a small amount of detrital quartz, but higher concentrations (ca. 1.3–2.7 wt.%) testify for a weak silicification in some samples.

The first group of pre-eruption late Eocene corals show REE concentrations that resemble largely the seawater pattern with light REE depletion, positive La and negative Ce anomalies (McLennan, 1989; Zhao and Jones, 2013; Li and Jones, 2014; Luo *et al.*, 2021). The second group of Oligocene corals tends to have entirely different flat pattern of higher REE abundances with pronounced enrich-

Fig. 4. Normalized to post-Archean Australian shale PAAS (Taylor and McLennan, 1985) REE contents of the studied samples of coral skeletons.

Table 1

Whole-rock chemical compositions of the coral samples

Sample	M	M1	K2	K2a	K2b	K3	K4	K6	K6a	D
Genera	Leptoseris	Favites	Cladocora	Colpophyllia	Porites	Cladocora	Cladocora	Porites	Cladocora	Cladocora
Location	41°24'15.2" 26°13'07.9"	41°24'15.2" 26°13'07.9"	41°48'9.6" 26°11'0.9"	41°48'9.6" 26°11'0.9"	41°48'9.6" 26°11'0.9"	41°45'12.8" 26°13'7.4"	41°31'30.84" 26°06'42.98"	41°42'5.5" 25°55'2.6"	41°42'5.5" 25°55'2.6"	41°21'05.21" 26°29'11.91"
SiO ₂	1.69	1.15	0.56	0.49	0.58	0.98	2.70	1.30	1.59	0.90
TiO ₂	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.01
Al ₂ O ₃	0.53	0.31	0.10	0.08	0.10	0.24	0.88	0.38	0.48	0.25
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.25	0.26	0.06	0.05	0.07	0.16	0.41	0.51	0.43	0.15
MnO	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.02
MgO	1.24	1.07	0.28	0.19	0.27	0.48	0.98	0.99	1.21	0.32
CaO	53.12	53.63	55.51	55.91	55.73	54.94	52.26	53.29	52.84	54.71
Na ₂ O	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01
K ₂ O	0.05	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.07	0.02	0.03	0.00
P ₂ O ₅	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.05
LOI	42.93	43.38	43.36	43.17	43.14	43.07	42.53	43.34	43.26	43.56
Total	99.88	99.87	99.91	99.92	99.93	99.95	99.94	99.91	99.92	99.98
Nb	1	0.40	0.47	0.47	0.36	0.39	1	1	1	0.42
Cd	4	5.69	6.17	13	4.69	4.67	4.15	4.17	7.46	5.37
Y	1	1	0.4	1	1	1	2	4	1	1
Rb	3	1	0.43	0.43	0.33	1	4	3	3	1
Sr	1380	1506	966	906	779	532	672	1044	938	233
Ba	19	15	17	18	30	14	29	14	15	12
U	2	1	0.35	0.4	1	1	1	2	1	1
Th	0.29	0.30	0.35	0.34	0.27	0.37	0.50	0.32	0.30	0.31
Pb	3	5	6	3	24	5	2	3	3	2
Sc	3.50	2.90	4.98	5.24	3.38	2.94	4	3.48	2.66	5
Li	1.43	2.08	0.17	0.24	0.22	2.08	1.18	0.20	1	2.04
B	35	46.66	44.20	35.40	60	37.50	40.87	32.66	47.28	39.50
Cr	34	30.70	35.72	36	50	34.28	41	47	39	41
V	26	24	20	19	21	25	31	40	26	24
Ni	27.53	27.86	31.25	30.18	23.98	26.63	30.29	30.50	26.24	29.26
Ga	1.13	1.07	1.23	2	1	1.42	2	1.95	1.89	2.23
Ge	6.33	6.40	7.55	7.46	7.54	7.89	6.95	7.03	6.06	6.75
As	4	4	6.04	6.02	4.32	3.82	4	4.61	4.56	3.77
Se	8.76	9.76	12.87	12.85	8.43	8.99	16.09	9.65	8.29	9.69
Zn	31	21	38	31	53	21	21	28	33	13.35
Cu	4	5	3.82	3.75	2.90	4.02	5	4.01	3.18	4.64
Co	1	0.80	0.84	2	1	1	2	1	1	1
La	1	1	0.36	0.35	1	0.50	1	6	1	1
Ce	3	2	0.50	0.40	1	1	2	11	2	1
Pr	0.30	0.25	0.29	0.29	0.22	0.24	0.40	1	0.30	0.27
Nd	1.59	2	1.88	1.84	1.43	1.57	1.77	5	1.49	1.71
Sm	1.90	1.93	2.23	2.19	1.70	1.86	2.11	2.08	1.79	2.02
Eu	0.52	0.53	0.61	0.60	0.46	0.51	0.58	0.57	0.48	0.56
Gd	2.03	2.07	2.39	2.34	1.82	2	2.44	2.21	1.89	2.18
Tb	0.30	0.30	0.35	0.34	0.27	0.29	0.33	0.33	0.28	0.32
Dy	1.24	1.26	1.45	1.42	1.10	1.21	1.37	1.36	1.16	1.32
Ho	0.31	0.31	0.36	0.35	0.27	0.30	0.34	0.33	0.29	0.33
Er	1.36	1.38	1.60	1.58	1.22	1.33	1.51	1.63	1.28	1.45
Tm	0.28	0.29	0.33	0.33	0.25	0.28	0.31	0.31	0.26	0.30
Yb	1.82	1.86	2.15	2.09	1.64	1.80	2.04	1.98	1.69	1.97
Lu	0.29	0.30	0.35	0.34	0.37	0.29	0.33	0.32	0.27	0.32

Major elements (wt.%) determined by XRF; trace elements and REE (ppm) analyzed by LA-ICP-MS.

Fig. 5. Variation diagrams of the elements in the studied samples: a) Σ REY–Al diagram; b) Fe–Al diagram; c) Mg–Al diagram; d) Fe–Mn diagram; e) Sr–Mg diagram; f) Σ REY–Ba diagram.

ment in heavy REE that point to a different course of history after the carbonate precipitation. In addition, all the samples analyzed are characterized by a low (<2) Mg/Ca molar ratio (Stanley *et al.*,

2002; Huang *et al.*, 2019) which is a clear proof for alteration of the original aragonite to a diagenetic low-magnesium calcite and the related modification of coral skeleton REE composition (Li and Jones,

2014; Luo *et al.*, 2021). In this regard, the distinctly different REE patterns of the second group without pronounced La and Ce anomalies can be attributed to either diagenetic modification (Frimmel, 2009) or inheritance from the original precipitates, but their pattern does not share similarities with the seawater source. Σ REY increase in carbonates has been reported when aragonite transformed to calcite (Webb *et al.*, 2009; Azmy *et al.*, 2011; Li and Jones, 2014); on the other hand, the elevated concentrations may have been produced as a result of terrigenous input.

The third group of Oligocene corals shows a similar but even flatter REE pattern than the second group and considerable enrichment in light over heavy REE. In this respect, several factors could explain elevated values of Σ REY in carbonates: 1) the higher the concentrations of REY in the initial sediment source the higher their amount in the lithified rock; 2) furthermore, the Σ REY enrichment in carbonates can result from a higher supply of Fe and Mn oxides; or 3) higher terrigenous input during diagenesis (Li and Jones, 2014); although 4) weathered carbonates tend to accumulate more terrigenous components around exposed surfaces (Luo *et al.*, 2021). Since Al is terrigenous in origin (Matson, 1989), higher concentration (Al > 100 ppm) of Al could reflect higher detrital influx. In the variation diagrams in Fig. 5, it is demonstrated a relation between the contents of Al, Fe, Mn and Σ REY, where there is a clear correlation between increasing Al along with Fe and Σ REY from the pre-eruption to eruption-associated reefs, and there is no visible connection between concentrations of Fe and Mn. Magnesium also follows the trend of increasing together with the higher uptake of terrigenous components in the depositional environment, while Sr demonstrates dispersed trends and, possibly, has been affected by the diagenetic alteration of aragonite to low-magnesium calcite, since low-magnesium calcite tends to retain lower concentrations of Sr after alteration. In the light of the discussed above, the increasing concentrations of Al and Fe from pre-eruption to eruption-associated reefs are highly likely to reflect incorporation of suspended detrital sediments rich in iron and aluminium minerals into the skeletal pores during and/or after organism growth, as revealed by microscopic investigations of corals that detrital sediments can be trapped into the skeleton cavities (Barnard *et al.*, 1974).

In any case, variations in local depositional environment is critical to determine the carbonate composition and is the most likely reason for the variations of Σ REY concentrations (Li and Jones, 2014). The continental detrital influx in the proximal sec-

tion is also reflected by overall higher REE and Al contents, as well as a tendency towards uniform, flat shale-normalized Σ REY patterns (Frimmel, 2009). From stratigraphic point of view, the Krumovgrad eruption-associated reefs represent a distal section compared to the Ivaylovgrad pre-eruption coral edifices that must have been located in the near-shore zone. This is further confirmed by the presence of diverse foraminifera in the Krumovgrad coral interseptal space that appears to be an indication of a greater depth (Araujo and Machado, 2008). In this sense, the elevated Ba content in the pre-eruption coral reefs can be explained by a higher concentration gradient of terrestrial run-off in the near-shore zone (Shen and Sanford, 1990), which is not registered in other terrigenous elements relative to the distal section of the Krumovgrad reefs. Therefore, the elevated abundances of REE and terrigenous elements cannot be attributed to solely coastal influx of detrital material and other sources located towards open sea should be considered potential candidates to clarify the composition of eruption-associated reefs.

The nearby-located Zvezdel paleovolcano can make such a candidate for contributing to the increase in Al and REE for the Krumovgrad reef edifices. Aluminium, which is abundant in magmatic rocks, can be used as a tracer of volcanic input (Siklós *et al.*, 2009; Wu *et al.*, 2018). As it is predicted by laboratory experiments, high amounts of aluminium can be released while tephra enters surface seawater (Frogner Kockum *et al.*, 2006). Pronounced increase in Al, as well as light REE, was documented in corals from the coastal site in central Vietnam and the open-ocean atoll in the central South China Sea following the eruption of Mount Pinatubo in the summer of 1991 (Wu *et al.*, 2018). REE signature of the corals reveals a gradual transformation from a typical seawater-like REE pattern to a peculiar LREE-enriched and HREE-depleted pattern. Such a pattern could result from a mixture of tephra and seawater compositions that became incorporated into the coral skeleton (Sholkovitz *et al.*, 1994).

To sum up, the chemical fingerprint of all samples from pre-eruption, eruption-associated and Metaxades-Didymotycho reefs speaks of diagenetically modified compositions related to the alteration of primary aragonite to diagenetic low-magnesium calcite. While terrestrial control on diagenetic modification is supposed to be registered in the increase in some terrigenous elements, like Al, Fe and REE, it is not confirmed by others, such as Ba which decreases from proximal pre-eruption to distal erup-

tion-associated reefs. This correlation questions the purely terrigenous origin of Al, Fe and REE in the eruption-associated reefs and links them to, presumably, contribution from a different source of prior diagenetic nature. This source is highly likely to be related to the nearby Zvezdel paleovolcano, which appears to have affected the chemical composition of the eruption-associated reefs. The negative Ce anomaly, which characterizes the pre-eruption reefs, probably reflects the seawater composition of the open late Eocene–early Oligocene marine basin covering the Eastern Rhodope–Thrace region in a similar way as in present-day South China Sea as described by Wu *et al.* (2018).

CONCLUSIONS

1. Coral assemblages in the studied reef buildups of the Eastern Rhodope–Thrace region are dominated by *Cladocora* sp., which is accompanied by *Porites* sp., *Colpophyllia* sp., *Favites* sp. and *Leptoseris* sp.

2. Based on field relations, the reefs can be subdivided into eruption-associated reefs (Krumovgrad) and pre-eruption reefs (Ivaylovgrad, Metaxades, Didymotycho). However, based on the REE abundances, three compositional groups can be identified: 1) REE patterns of pre-eruption reefs that have preserved composition pretty much similar to the seawater source; 2) REE patterns of

pre-eruption, eruption-associated and Metaxades-Didymotycho reefs showing increase in light REE that are related to diagenetic modification; and 3) REE patterns restricted to only eruption-associated reefs demonstrating enrichment in light over heavy REE that highly likely have taken contribution from a different source of prior diagenetic nature along with subsequent diagenetic modification. The increase in ΣREY from pre-eruption to eruption-associated reefs is well correlated with elevated amounts of terrigenous elements like Al and Fe.

3. Barium, which is more abundant in the near-shore pre-eruption reefs, does not confirm connection between the increasing amount of terrigenous elements and REE in the distal eruption-associated reefs to have resulted from terrestrial discharge/continental runoff and most likely indicates volcanic contribution to the seawater and chemistry of coral skeletons.

Acknowledgements

The study was supported by the Sofia University “St Kliment Ohridski” Science Fund research grant No. 80-10-10/18.03.2021. The authors thank Dr Vyara Idakieva (Sofia University “St Kliment Ohridski”) for her help with the taxonomic determination of the corals. We thank two anonymous reviewers for careful reading and commenting on the manuscript.

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